

GENDER AS THE LINGUISTIC TERM

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Abstract. *This article deals with the formation of the term gender, its difference from the term sex and its role and importance in the field of linguistic investigations. Moreover. Biological certain specific peculiarities of the term gender will be discussed in this article.*

Keywords: *linguistic term, English language, gender studies.*

ГЕНДЕР КАК ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКИЙ ТЕРМИН

Аннотация. *В данной статье речь идет о формировании термина «гендер», его отличии от термина «пол», его роли и значения в области лингвистических исследований. Более того. В данной статье будут рассмотрены некоторые биологические особенности термина «гендер».*

Ключевые слова: *лингвистический термин, английский язык, гендерные исследования.*

There have been three paradigms in the historical development of linguistics such as system-structural, comparative-typological and anthropocentric ones. The appearance of gender linguistics is a result of anthropocentric paradigm which is based on the role of human being as the user of a language. Gender investigations first appeared in the sixties and seventies of the twentieth century in the Western European countries and the USA.

One of the founders of the discipline gender studies was R. Lakoff who is considered to be a pioneer in the field of language and gender. The author claimed that several distinctive features of women's language exist. In 1973 Lakoff published an article on language and gender which later on linguists started considering this issue as gender linguistics. According to the author there were a number of words in women's speech which are not found in men's speech. Women often sounded as they were asking questions when they were making statements, their sentences ended with rising intonation in comparison with male pronunciation, women used to ask more questions, namely tag questions than men did. A tag question is a kind of polite statement which does not force agreement or belief on the addressee. A request may be in the same sense of a polite command, which does not require obedience, but rather suggests something be done as a favor to the speaker. Moreover, women often tended to use emphatic modifiers as so, very, such.

According to Russian linguist E. Goroshko the term gender is taken from the Greek word «genos» which means «origin, an heir is born». It is considered to be the object of different disciplines such as monies, social studies, history, anthropology, psychology, sociolinguistics and psycholinguistics. The problem of gender differentiation depends on the role of a certain gender in social and other branches of life. In most cases the term gender is used when dealing with intergender differentiations according to many gender theories. It is the gender that distinguishes a male from a female. So, the term gender plays an essential role in different spheres of human life. Besides that, gender is out of the main notions of contemporary gender linguistics.

There are a lot of basic notions of gender studies; gender, sex, gender display, gender role, gender stereotypes, gender system and gender linguistic personality.

It goes without saying that the main problem among above mentioned notions of gender linguistics is the distinction between the terms gender and sex. Sex means a biological sex which is usually understood to be as one of the birth half, or each of the two genetically and physiologically opposite living beings, organisms. (каждый из двух генетически и физиологически противопоставленных разрядов живых существ (мужчин и женщин, самцов и самок), организмов).

As for sociologists, they usually state three types of approaches in the study of existence and specific features of sex: biological, structural or role playing and symbolic foundations.

Scientists of Moscow center of gender studies give the following definitions of the term gender: 1. (in general sense) the difference between men and women according to anatomy sex. 2. (Social sense) social division which usually based on anatomic sex but not always coincides with it. So, sociological use of term may differ from its use in everyday life.

The term gender is understood as the relation which demonstrates belonging to a certain class, group, and category. Gender constructs the relation between one object (or a thing) and the other expressing the same class or group.

According to IV. Groshev the notion of gender implies the sum of presentations or expectations connected in the society as «womanhood» and «man- hood». Genderization put a certain demarcation line in behavioral features between man and woman. As the words manhood and womanhood express a lot of connotational meanings they can be used in different spheres of human life whereas their equivalents feminine and masculine are considered to be terms specific for certain field of study, for instance in linguistics which means either a grammatical or lexical category. A set of psychosocial characteristics of personality traditionally considered to be typical for a woman/man (as the representatives of biological sex) is understood by the terms of feminine and masculine in Gender linguistics.

Some researchers believe that the difference between the notions «sex» and «gender», in fact depends on the distinction of biological and social aspects. Biological difference (sexual features) depends on internal features, as individual features des elope in certain individuals and remain constant till the end of its wholehfe. Social masculism and feminity, ie, gender differences begin to develop after being born. C. Miller and K. Swift explain this process as follows: too simplifying the explanation. it is possible to state that a sex is biological data where a gender is a social norm. According to the authors over implication risk appears as sex and gender are closely connected with each other. Gender distinctions are partly based on sexual ones. A woman traditionally acquires a social role of mother which is the result of biological functions of bringing up children. Man is usually responsible for heavy physical labor in society as he is stronger than a woman from biological point of view. It is absolutely evident that there are only certain social functions based on sex, most of them is a result of cultural behavior. One of the most disputable problems arose in the struggle for an equal social right is observed in social - cultural stereotypes: the role of a mother can fully be performed with the role of a lawyer or a bus driver, and physical labor can be connected with cooking or ironing. So, the number of social roles based on sexual distinction is rather fewer than before.

Sociolinguists, psycholinguists and many other scholars have often difficulty in the differentiation of notions sex and gender. So, P. Eckert states the following on this occasion: «The difference between men and women is a gender function and only indirectly a sexual. We

(sociolinguists) study a gender and its all changes paying attention to the connection of gender with sex to most extend rather than gender differences. This is the result of the role and importance of gender being changeable and complex notion in society.>>

We fully agree with the abovementioned opinion.

The notion of gender appeared in linguistics via the assimilation of English term gender. The aim of assimilation was the differentiation of notions gender and sex (as biological sex) as the term gender is linked with natural determination not only body difference of men and women but also labor division by broils, different requirements and relations of society towards men and women. that The term gender is used to state not natural, but socio-cultural reasons in inter sexual difference.

There are a number of reasons in the necessity of methodological difference of sex (biological) from gender (social) according to N. Khodyreva:

-first of all, widespread opinions and belief that social position is a result of biological one, a sexual difference (sex-genetic composition, reproduceable anatomy and functions);

-secondly, sex and gender are interrelated and interacted in the process of life circle (ontogenies)

-Thirdly, social gender is easy to change than biological. So, gender can be included into the social change practice

Gender can not be formed by means of nature, but it is constructed by society etc. it is the product of our social doing.

The term gender returned to linguistics with its new meaning recently when gender investigations achieved the status of interdisciplinary character. Moreover, before the formation of the term gender linguistic semantics did not ignore the reflection of the notion of sex in a language in the meaning of sexus as the semantic component «sexus» was included in the semantic structure of a number of lexical units (man, woman, mother, father, husband. wife, etc.). So, there appears the necessity to explain how these notions are related to each other in linguistics as sexus and gender functions more clearly than other social disciplines dealing with gender investigations.

A number of scholars assimilate the notion gender with a social status, Gender which is often called as social sexus differing from a biological sexus is studied as one of the basic measurements of social structure of a given society together with class belonging, age and other characteristics organizing a social system. Gender is a social status which determines individual abilities in education, professional career, access to power, sexuality, family roles and reproduction process. Social status functions in the frame of cultural space of a given society. This means that gender culture corresponds with gender status,"

As is seen, three groups of characteristics such as biological sex, role sterfus types, gender display form gender as a social construction.

Thus, sex is a biological belonging of personality, whereas gender can be defined as social component of psycholinguistic model of behavior.

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